

Antibody Characterization Report for PLC-gamma-2 (PLCG2)

YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report

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Target:

Recommended protein name: 1-phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate phosphodiesterase gamma-2

Short protein name: PLC-gamma-2

Alternative protein name: Phosphoinositide phospholipase C-gamma-2, Phospholipase C-IV, Phospholipase C-gamma-2

Gene name: *PLCG2*

Uniprot: P16885

We are a third-party organization with the mission to characterize commercial antibodies for all human protein through open science [1]. In this study, we characterized eleven PLC-gamma-2 commercial antibodies for Western Blot, immunoprecipitation, and immunofluorescence using a standardized experimental protocol [2] based on comparing read-outs in knockout cell lines and isogenic parental controls. We identified many well-performing antibodies and encourage readers to use this report as a guide to select the most appropriate antibody for their specific needs. A custom THP-1 *PLCG2* KO line from Abcam was used in this study. Expression of PLC-gamma-2 protein in THP-1 is adequate as determined by searching DepMap [3].

The authors do not provide an assessment of the quality of the tested antibodies as their respective performances are limited to our finite experimental conditions. The readers should interpret the present findings based on their own scientific expertise. The authors acknowledge that an antibody that demonstrates specificity in the stated test conditions can be suboptimal in a different experimental format or in cell lines that differ from those directly tested here.

Table 1: Summary of the cell lines used

Institution	Catalog number	RRID (Cellosaurus)	Cell line	Genotype
Abcam	ab271147	CVCL_0006	THP-1	WT
Abcam	ab308482	-	THP-1	<i>PLCG2</i> KO

Table 2: Summary of the PLC-gamma-2 antibodies tested

Company	Catalog number	Lot number	RRID (Antibody Registry)	Clonality	Clone ID	Host	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{l}$)	Vendors recommended applications
Abcam	ab109267**	GR498527	AB_10888119	recombinant-mono	EPR1403	rabbit	1.32	Wb
Abcam	ab133522**	GR962819	AB_2927390	recombinant-mono	EPR5914-34	rabbit	0.63	Wb
Bio-Techne	MAB3716*	XXN0319021	AB_2163529	monoclonal	346404	mouse	0.50	Wb,IF
Bio-Techne	NBP2-52536*	141225	AB_2927391	monoclonal	2D9E8	mouse	1.00	Wb,IF
Cell Signaling Technology	3872	5	AB_2299586	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.12	Wb,IP
Cell Signaling Technology	34264**	1	AB_2927393	recombinant-mono	E7L6G	rabbit	0.39	Wb
Cell Signaling Technology	55512**	1	AB_2799488	recombinant-mono	E5U4T	rabbit	0.05	Wb,IP,IF
GeneTex	GTX111178	40058	AB_1951276	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.66	Wb,IF
GeneTex	GTX111293	43334	AB_1951274	polyclonal	-	rabbit	0.75	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-35670**	XH3670294	AB_2849570	recombinant-mono	ARC1176	rabbit	0.73	Wb
Thermo Fisher Scientific	MA5-38600*	XH3669859	AB_2898512	monoclonal	2D9E8	mouse	1.00	Wb,IF

Wb=Western blot, IP= immunoprecipitation, IF=immunofluorescence, *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Materials and methods

Antibodies

All tested PLC-gamma-2 antibodies are listed in Table 2. Peroxidase-conjugated anti-rabbit and goat anti-mouse are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 65-6120 and 62-6520). Alexa-555-conjugated anti-rabbit and goat anti-mouse secondary antibodies are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A21429 and A21424).

Cell culture

Cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 medium (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number 11875119) containing 10% fetal bovine serum (Wisent, cat. number 080450), 2 mM L-glutamate (Wisent, cat. number 609065), 100 IU penicillin and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (Wisent, cat. number 450201).

THP-1 WT and *PLCG2* KO (listed in Table 1) were treated with 200 ng/ml of phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) (Abcam, cat. number ab147465) for 2 days. 200 ng/ml of PMA was added to fresh medium in both day 1 and day 2 [4].

Antibody screening by Western Blot

Western Blots were performed as described in our standard operating procedure [5]. THP-1 WT and *PLCG2* KO were collected in RIPA buffer (25mM Tris-HCl pH 7.6, 150mM NaCl, 1% NP-40, 1% sodium deoxycholate, 0.1% SDS) supplemented with 1x protease inhibitor cocktail mix (MilliporeSigma, cat. number P8340). Lysates were sonicated briefly and incubated 30 min on ice. Lysates were spun at ~110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C and equal protein aliquots of the supernatants were analyzed by SDS-PAGE and Western Blot. BLUelf prestained protein ladder from GeneDireX (cat. number PM008-0500) was used.

Western Blots were performed with precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number WXP42012BOX) ran with Tris/Glycine/SDS buffer from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1610772), loaded in Laemmli loading sample buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number AAJ61337AD) and transferred on nitrocellulose membranes. Proteins on the blots were visualized with Ponceau S staining (Thermo Fisher Scientific, cat. number BP103-10) which is scanned to show together with individual Western Blot. Blots were blocked with 5% milk for 1 hr, and antibodies were incubated O/N at 4°C with 5% milk in TBS with 0,1% Tween 20 (TBST) from Cell Signaling (cat. number 9997). Following three washes with TBST, the peroxidase conjugated secondary antibody was incubated at a dilution of ~0.2 µg/ml in

TBST with 5% milk for 1 hr at room temperature followed by three washes with TBST. Membranes are incubated with Pierce ECL from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 32106) or Clarity Western ECL Substrate from Bio-Rad (cat. number 1705061) prior to detection with the iBright™ CL1500 Imaging System from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number A44240).

Antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Immunoprecipitation was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [6]. Antibody-bead conjugates were prepared by adding 2 µg or 10 µl of antibodies 3872 and 55512** to 500 µl of Pierce IP Lysis Buffer from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 87788) in a microcentrifuge tube, together with with 30µl of Dynabeads protein A- (for rabbit antibodies) or protein G- (for mouse antibodies) from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number 10002D and 10004D, respectively). Tubes were rocked for ~1 hr at 4°C followed by several washes to remove unbound antibodies.

THP-1 WT were collected in Pierce IP buffer (25 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1% NP-40 and 5% glycerol) supplemented with protease inhibitor. Lysates are rocked 30 min at 4°C and spun at 110,000xg for 15 min at 4°C. 0.5 ml aliquots at 2.0 mg/ml of lysate were incubated with an antibody-bead conjugate for ~1 hr at 4°C. The unbound fractions were collected, and beads were subsequently washed three times with 1.0 ml of IP lysis buffer and processed for SDS-PAGE and Western Blot on precast midi precast midi 4-20% Tris-Glycine polyacrylamide gels from Thermo Fisher Scientific.

Antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Immunofluorescence was performed as described in our standard operating procedure [7]. THP-1 WT and *PLCG2* KO were labelled with a green and a far-red fluorescence dye, respectively. The fluorescent dyes used are from Thermo Fisher Scientific (cat. number C2925 and C34565). WT and KO cells were plated in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. (Perkin Elmer, cat. number 6055300) as a mosaic and incubated for 24 hrs in a cell culture incubator. Cells were fixed in 4% PFA (in PBS) for 15 min at room temperature and then washed 3 times with PBS. Cells were permeabilized in PBS with 0,1% Triton X-100 for 10 min at room temperature and blocked with PBS with 5% BSA, 5% goat serum and 0.01% Triton X-100 for 30 min at room temperature. Cells were incubated with IF buffer (PBS, 5% BSA, 0,01% Triton X-100) containing the primary PLC-gamma-2 antibodies O/N at 4°C. Cells were then washed 3 × 10 min with IF buffer and incubated with corresponding Alexa Fluor 555-conjugated

secondary antibodies in IF buffer at a dilution of 1.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for 1 hr at room temperature with DAPI. Cells were washed 3 \times 10 min with IF buffer and once with PBS.

Images were acquired on an ImageXpress micro widefield high-content microscopy system (Molecular Devices), using a 20x NA 0.95 water immersion objective and scientific CMOS cameras, equipped with 395, 475, 555 and 635 nm solid state LED lights (lumencor Aura III light engine) and bandpass filters to excite DAPI, Cellmask Green, Alexa568 and Cellmask Red, respectively. Images had pixel sizes of 0.68 \times 0.68 microns, and a z-interval of 4 microns. For analysis and visualization, shading correction (shade only) was carried out for all images. Then, maximum intensity projections were generated using 3 z-slices. Segmentation was carried out separately on maximum intensity projections of Cellmask channels using CellPose 1.0, and masks were used to generate outlines and for intensity quantification. Figures were assembled with Adobe Illustrator.

Figure 1: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by Western Blot

Figure 2: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation

Figure 3: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence

Figure 1: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by Western Blot.

Lysates of THP-1 WT and *PLCG2* KO treated or not with PMA were prepared, and 10 µg of protein were processed for Western Blot with the indicated PLC-gamma-2 antibodies. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. All antibodies were tested at a dilution of 1/500 except antibody 34264** was used at 1/200. Predicted band size: 148 kDa. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 2: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by immunoprecipitation.

THP-1 lysates were prepared, and immunoprecipitation was performed using 2.0 µg of the indicated PLC-gamma-2 antibodies pre-coupled to Dynabeads protein A or protein G. Samples were washed and processed for Western Blot with the indicated PLC-gamma-2 antibody. For Western Blot, 55512** was used at 1/500. The Ponceau stained transfers of each blot are shown. SM=4% starting material; UB=4% unbound fraction; IP=immunoprecipitate. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

Figure 3: PLC-gamma-2 antibody screening by immunofluorescence.

THP-1 WT and *PLCG2* KO cells were labelled with a green or a far-red fluorescent dye, respectively. WT and KO cells were mixed and plated to a 1:1 ratio in a 96-well plate with optically clear flat-bottom. Cells were stained with the indicated PLC-gamma-2 antibodies and with the corresponding Alexa-fluor 555 coupled secondary antibody including DAPI. Acquisition of the blue (nucleus-DAPI), green (identification of WT cells), red (antibody staining) and far-red (identification of KO cells) channels was performed. Representative images of the blue and red (grayscale) channels are shown. WT and KO cells are outlined with green and magenta dashed line, respectively. Antibodies were tested at 1.0 µg/ml. Bars = 10 µm. *=monoclonal antibody, **=recombinant antibody

References

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